

Polarographic Behaviour of the Mixed Complexes Formed by Cd(II) with Gluconate-pyridine and Gluconate-itaconate Systems

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Schaap and McMasters method has been used to determine the overall formation constants of mixed ligand complexes formed by (a) Cd(II) with gluconate and itaconate and (b) Cd(II) with pyridine and gluconate. DeFord and Hume's treatment showed that Cd(II) forms three complex species each with pyridine, gluconate and itaconate ions. In both the mixed ligand systems the reductions were reversible and diffusion controlled involving two electrons. Cd(II) forms three mixed ligand species $[Cd(X)(Y)]$; $[Cd(X)(Y)_2]$ and $[Cd(X)_2(Y)]$ with:

(a) $\beta_{11}=34$; $\beta_{12}=333$; $\beta_{21}=1750$ [glu-ita] and (b) $\beta_{11}=467$; $\beta_{12}=667$; $\beta_{21}=1050$ [glu-pyr].

Tendencies of various complexes to add and substitute another ligand is discussed.

MIXED ligand complexes have been studied by potentiometric¹⁻² and spectrophotometric measurements³⁻⁴ and by pH titration curves⁵. Schaap and McMasters⁶ have extended the technique of polarography by a logical extension of DeFord and Hume's⁷ method by applying the latter to cases where a metal ion forms complex with two ligands simultaneously in solution.

The practical determination of stability constants involves many more measurements than the straight forward DeFord and Hume's approach and can be somewhat tedious. The mixed complexes of Cd(II) with various organic ligands have been studied in our laboratory⁸⁻¹⁰. It was found that Cd(II) forms 1:3 highest complexes with pyridine, gluconate and itaconate ions. Present paper deals with the mixed ligand studies of Cd(II) with (a) gluconate-itaconate and (b) gluconate-pyridine at d.m.e.

Experimental

Sodium gluconate, sodium itaconate and pyridine were used as complexing agents whereas NaClO₄ served as supporting electrolyte to maintain constant ionic strength [$\mu=1.5$]. All the measurements were carried out at $293 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{K}$ which was maintained by Haake type ultrathermostat. The solution was placed in an H-type cell coupled with saturated calomel electrode through an agar-agar saturated with NaCl salt bridge. Prior to reduction at d.m.e., purified nitrogen gas streamed through the test solution for 20 minutes to expel the dissolved oxygen. The polarograms were obtained on a

manual set up. The d.m.e. used has the following characteristics: $m=2.10$ mg/sec., $t=3.0$ seconds (at -1.0 V vs S.C.E. in 1M NaClO₄) was used throughout the course of investigation.

Results and Discussion

Cd(II) produces a single, well developed wave in each solution. The plots of i_x vs \sqrt{h} (h =effective height of mercury column) are linear and pass through the origin. The plots of $\log \frac{i}{i_a - i}$ Vs E . were linear with a slope of $32+1$ mV. Thus, the reduction was diffusion controlled and found reversible involving two electrons. The overall formation constants of simple complexes were determined by DeFord and Hume's method using the polarographic measurements. The results are summarised as below:

System	Overall formation constant		
	β_1	β_2	β_3
Cd(II)-Gluconate	5	39	200
Cd(II)-Pyridine	40	80	990
Cd(II)-Itaconate	20	160	1760

The polarographic characteristics and Fij function values of the mixed Cd(II)-itaconate-gluconate system at fixed gluconate concentrations of 0.2 and 0.3M are summarised in Table 1, whereas Table 2 presents the polarographic characteristics and Fij function values of the mixed Cd(II)-pyridine-gluconate system at fixed gluconate-concentrations of 0.2 and 0.3M respectively.

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF Cd(II)-ITACONATE-GLUCONATE-SYSTEM AT 293°K ($\mu = 1.5$)

*C _x	Glucuronate ion concentration = 0.2M					Glucuronate ion concentration = 0.3M						
	E _½	i _d	F ₀₀ (X)	F ₁₀ (X)	F ₂₀ (X)	F ₃₀ (X)	E _½	i _d	F ₀₀ (X)	F ₁₀ (X)	F ₂₀ (X)	F ₃₀ (X)
	(-Vvs S.C.E.)	(μ A)					(-Vvs S.C.E.)	(μ A)				
0	0.582	2.82	-	-	-	-	0.582	2.82	-	-	-	-
0.05	0.606	2.42	7.71	34.14	-	-	0.612	2.35	12.71	54.18	-	-
0.10	0.613	2.35	13.75	77.51	375	-	0.618	2.29	20.98	109.76	498	-
0.15	0.622	2.24	29.31	155.39	769	1793	0.626	2.20	40.97	206.52	976	1842
0.20	0.628	2.18	48.44	212.21	861	1805	0.631	2.05	64.64	273.22	1066	1830
0.25	0.633	2.07	75.67	278.67	954	1818	0.636	2.02	97.93	351.72	1167	1867
0.30	3.638	2.06	112.16	353.87	1046	1820	0.640	1.91	141.97	439.90	1066	1888
0.35	0.642	2.00	158.79	436.56	1133	1808	0.644	1.88	196.80	533.71	1351	1860

A=6 ; B=40 ; C=500 ; D=1810

A=10 ; B=60 ; C=700 ; D=1860

*C_x¹ = Concentration itaconate ions in moles/litre.

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF Cd(II)-PYRIDINE-GLUCONATE SYSTEM AT 293°K ($\mu = 1.5$)

*C _x	Glucuronate ion concentration = .2M					Glucuronate ion concentration = 0.3M						
	E _½	i _d	F ₀₀ (X)	F ₁₀ (X)	F ₂₀ (X)	F ₃₀ (X)	E _½	i _d	F ₀₀ (X)	F ₁₀ (X)	F ₂₀ (X)	F ₃₀ (X)
	(-Vvs S.C.E.)	(μ A)					(-Vvs S.C.E.)	(μ A)				
0	0.582	2.82	-	-	-	-	0.582	2.82	-	-	-	-
0.1	0.622	2.38	27.66	176.6	-	-	0.625	2.09	39.88	248.8	-	-
0.2	0.630	2.24	55.02	225.1	325	-	0.633	1.95	79.96	323.7	419	-
0.3	0.638	2.09	110.97	336.6	588	995	0.640	1.80	150.74	452.5	708	1027
0.4	0.644	2.04	181.83	429.6	675	962	0.646	1.79	243.24	570.6	827	1066
0.5	0.649	1.95	281.78	543.6	768	956	0.651	1.75	367.41	704.8	930	1060
0.6	0.654	1.91	427.41	695.7	893	1005	0.655	1.63	541.05	876.8	1061	1102
0.7	0.658	1.84	606.76	852.5	987	999	0.659	1.60	756.74	1059.6	1170	1101

A=10 ; B=160 ; C=290 ; D=1000

A=15 ; B=240 ; C=400 ; D=1070.

*C_x = Concentration of pyridine in moles/litre.

The composition and formation constants for the mixed ligand systems have been evaluated by Schaap McMasters' treatment which has been discussed in details earlier⁸. In both the systems, Cd(II) forms three mixed ligand species :

[Cd(X)(Y)] ; [Cd(X)(Y)₂] and [Cd(H)₂(X)] with :

- (a) $\beta_{11} = 34$; $\beta_{12} = 333$; $\beta_{21} = 1750$ and
- (b) $\beta_{11} = 467$; $\beta_{12} = 667$; $\beta_{21} = 1050$ respectively.

Cd(II) forms three mixed complexes, existing in solution having following equilibria. The numerical values represent log K [where K is the equilibrium constant of the step indicated in the summary].

In this scheme X⁻¹ and Y⁻² stand for gluconate and itaconate ions respectively. From the scheme, it is seen that [Cd(Y)]⁺ can add Y⁻² as well as X⁻¹

but the results show that the addition of the latter is easier. The two unsaturated complexes [Cd(X)]⁺ and [Cd(Y)] can add Y⁻² and X⁻¹ respectively forming the mixed complex [Cd(X)(Y)]⁻¹. The relative tendencies of addition reveal that Y⁻² is stronger ligand than X⁻¹ (see the step constants). The unsaturated mixed complex [Cd(X)(Y)]⁻¹ can add itself X⁻¹ as well as Y⁻². The addition of Y⁻² is, however, easier than X⁻¹. [Cd(Y)] can add X⁻¹ as well as Y⁻² but the addition of Y⁻² is easier than that of X⁻¹. This shows clearly that the mixed complex formation is preferred over the simple. Saturated simple complex [Cd(X)₂]⁻¹ can accommodate Y⁻² in place of X⁻¹ to form [Cd(X)₂(Y)]⁻². Therefore, we conclude that in presence of two different ligands the metal ion preferably forms mixed complexes.

In this scheme (b) X^{-1} and Y represent gluconate and pyridine respectively. From the equilibrium constant values given in the scheme, we can discuss various relative tendencies of mixed complexation similarly.

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